

Note: We have revised the scope, milestones and deliverables of the project from the original proposal, based on a revised amount of funding available for it.

Project Title: Incentivizing Investment in and Adoption of Open Infrastructure for Research through Community Health Assessments

Research Question (distinct): How applicable and useful are community health frameworks such as CHAOSS, FOREST, and POSI in incentivizing investment and adoption of open infrastructure for research?

Why is this important to answer (context)? We are focusing our work on the research ecosystem, where both open and proprietary tools help researchers create, disseminate, and preserve knowledge. Nonprofit and government sectors have built and supported a range of much-relied upon open research tools over the last three decades; however, nearly all of this “open” activity has been conducted with severely limited funding. Successful projects have often used a mixture of grants and low-cost institutional membership models to fund their initial emergence (piloting to production), but their growth predictably plateaus and becomes stunted as they age out of “innovation”-oriented grant opportunities and face a marketplace where “open” is too often interpreted as meaning “low- or no-revenue.” To thrive, open efforts need various types of operational and maintenance support; making these needs more visible through health measures may help to encourage important investments in these types of support. That visibility may also help to spotlight common needs that could be met through services designed to be shared by a subset of infrastructures.

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Start Date: January 13, 2025

Duration: 6/9/12 months? **12 months**

Milestones

Project Duration & PI/Team

- **Start Date:** January 13, 2025
- **Duration of Project:** 12 months
- **PI:** Katherine Skinner
- **Team Members:** Chrys Wu, Lauren Collister

1. (Milestone 1) Agreement Signature

- **Milestone:** January 2025

- Deliverable:
 - Agreement Signed

2. (Milestone 2) Ethnographic Study Documentation

- Milestone: June 2025
- Outputs
 - Survey and interview protocols
 - Summary analysis of survey and interview data
 - Selection of 10 relevant health measures/methods
 - Informational webinar

3. (Milestone 3) Release & Reporting

- Milestone: January 2026
- Outputs
 - Establish and model reporting mechanisms (including ways of visualizing results) for the 10 health measures/methods
 - Results for these 10 health measures/methods against existing Infra Finder dataset
 - Summary of Infra Finder infrastructures' evaluations of the accuracy and soundness of those 10 health measures
 - Final Report

Incentivizing Investment in and Adoption of Open Infrastructure for Research through Community Health Assessments

Digital Infrastructure Insights Fund (DIIF) 2024

Aim: to better understand how open digital infrastructure is built and deployed.

2024 RFP: proposals to study the rationales, production, use, governance and maintenance of open digital infrastructures.

Research Question

How applicable and useful are community health frameworks such as CHAOSS, FOREST, and POSI in incentivizing investment and adoption of open infrastructure for research?

Research Methods

We will deploy a mixed model utilizing ethnographic, qualitative, and quantitative research methods to identify, test, and evaluate ways of assessing the health of open tools, protocols, and standards commonly used in research environments (including academic libraries, research labs, and publishing). We will utilize surveys and structured interviews to identify initial health measures to apply to infrastructures included in our [Infra Finder dataset](#), which represents information on 57 infrastructures serving the research and scholarly communication ecosystem. Our work will result in resources and mappings that highlight important health signals within this market context to further investment in and adoption of infrastructures, and examine the implications and value of incorporating these measures into decision making tools like Infra Finder.

Phase 1: Conduct interviews and surveys. We will design and launch a health indicators survey for three key user groups: funders, open source community members (e.g. developers, technical leads, community managers, etc.), and adopters of open infrastructures within the research sector. Based on the survey results, we will design and host interviews to delve into the key concerns and drivers for each user group, including what factors incentivize or disincentivize them from investing in/adopting open source tools and what they see as strong health markers for this specific market. Interviewees (at least six per user group, or 18 total) will include perspectives from multiple sectors, including corporate, nonprofit, and government. They will help us to understand how and

whether using relevant measures from models such as [CHAOSS](#), the [FOREST Framework](#), and [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructures](#) (POSI) help to inform their decisions. Together, we will gauge how fit-for-purpose different health indicators are for our specific market context and set of infrastructures, and consider how these measures could be used to identify promising funding or intervention opportunities.

Phase 2: Test initial application of measures. We will model and test a set of up to 10 measures on the 57 infrastructures included in the [Infra Finder dataset](#), building on this existing dataset that we have compiled about governance, funding, organizational form, engagement, and technical maturity. Potential health measures to explore in concert with Infra Finder data include assessments of [bus factor](#), [development responsiveness](#), [business readiness](#), ["living will"](#), [financial and organizational resilience](#), and [transparent business practices](#). We will analyze the findings from these measures to surface meaningful stories and provide analysis on applicability and utility. Our findings will be based on 1) our team's analysis of the validity of these measures as applied to the infrastructures represented in Infra Finder; 2) co-evaluation of findings by the three user groups - funders, developers, and adopters and 3) co-evaluation of validity and usefulness of these measures by the community managers or leads of the open infrastructures that we represent in Infra Finder.

Phase 3: Documentation and next steps. Our work will result in resources and mappings that highlight important health signals and their potential value and implications within this market context for guiding intervention and investment opportunities.

Data and Resources

We will build upon key community frameworks - CHAOSS, FOREST, and POSI - investigating how questions derived from each might help to surface health factors of interest to our user communities (funders, developers, and adopters). We will also learn from and build on existing analyses of preliminary base-level applications of CHAOSS metrics to key infrastructures in this market (Colt 2023; Augspurger et al, 2023; Eghbal 2016).

We will also use data that we have collected in [Infra Finder](#), a tool designed to help organizations quickly see, compare, and share information crucial to the selection of infrastructures (including procurement processes) in this specific market. Infra Finder variables include costs, hosting options, governance, policies, organizational model(s), and funding needs of featured open infrastructures. This data has been jointly gathered and vetted by each infrastructure in close coordination with the IOI team.

We will generate data in surveys and interviews to identify initial health measures critical to understanding the health, sustainability, and survivability of open infrastructures. We will also generate and use co-evaluation data to refine and solidify these health measures and to test their efficacy.

Communities Targeted

This project targets the institutional support structures and decision makers most likely to fund and contribute labor to the creation, maintenance, and interoperability of various elements within the research ecosystem. We seek to increase investment in and adoption of the open solutions by all types of players in this market, including by commercial, government, and not-for-profit entities.

We are focusing our work on the research ecosystem, where both open and proprietary tools help researchers create, disseminate, and preserve knowledge. A range of open research tools have been built and supported over the last three decades; however, nearly all of this “open” activity has been undertaken by players in the nonprofit and government sectors with severely limited funding.

Successful projects have often used a mixture of grants and low-cost institutional membership models to fund their initial emergence (piloting to production), but their growth predictably plateaus and becomes stunted as they age out of “innovation”-oriented grant opportunities and face a marketplace where “open” is too often interpreted as meaning “low- or no-revenue.” To thrive, open efforts need various types of operational and maintenance support; making these needs more visible through health measures may help to encourage important investments in these types of support. That visibility may also help to spotlight common needs that could be met through services designed to be shared by a subset of infrastructures.

This project builds on multi-year efforts at IOI to gather, collate, and disseminate information about available open tools, standards, protocols, and services in order to gauge the health of individual projects and to identify potential portfolios or ecosystems that could maximize the impact of investments in open. Working in close collaboration with the funders, developers, and adopters of open has allowed us to amass initial data about governance, funding, organizational form, community engagement, roadmap maturity, and other key factors. What is currently missing - the crucial gap we seek to fill - is a clear understanding of what each of these three groups (funders, developers, and adopters) across sectors need to know in order to increase their investment and trust in open solutions (rather than proprietary ones) and to begin channeling their investments of time and resources differently.

General Workplan

Building on the Phases outlined in the research methods section above, we aim to undertake the following activities for this proposed project:

1. Design survey instrument(s); design target audience engagement strategies for three main user groups (funders, developers, and adopters) across multiple sectors (corporate, nonprofit, government).
2. Deploy survey (aiming for at least 150 respondents); conduct initial analysis
3. Design interview protocol, based on initial analysis and key emerging questions.
4. Select and recruit at least six representatives (18 total) from each of the user groups (funders, developers, and adopters) to participate in interviews. We will aim for an intentional mix of corporate, nonprofit, and government voices.
5. Conduct interviews; code and analyze interview data.
6. Select relevant health measures and methods based on findings and on existing options (e.g., CHAOSS, FOREST, POSI).
7. Bridge Infra Finder data (not the tool, just the data) with the selected metrics to test and model possible integrations of measures.
8. Establish reporting mechanisms (including ways of visualizing results) based on the identified variables, and document the potential points of investment/intervention that they might signal.
 - a. Some of these might be aimed at single tools; others may identify shared needs across multiple tools that could be ripe for investment and collaborative work (e.g., shared needs like marketing and sales that enable a stronger story and market presence to evolve for "open" in this market).
9. Conduct final evaluations by our project team; the funders, developers, and adopters of open source research infrastructures; and by all of the infrastructures currently represented in Infra Finder.
10. Refine, finalize, and share both the methods and the findings; establish clear next steps for integrating these new measures into Infra Finder and/or other tools.

Outreach Activities

For this project, we will be focusing on engaging representatives from the following user groups. Honoraria will be offered to help offset unpaid contributions to this research, and to further enable equitable participation across user groups.

- **Funders** - including public and private philanthropies, national research funders, government agencies, and commercial entities poised to invest financially in open infrastructure solutions. Funders incentivize particular types of short-term,

project-based activity and provide longer-term support for some successful keystone initiatives in the field. We will involve these entities to broaden our understanding of the limitations and pressures they face and the information they most need in order to motivate and maximize their investments.

- **Adopters** - including academic institutions and networks of active “open” participants in this market. Adopters support volunteer efforts and deployment activities; they are also advocates, encouraging others to adopt. We will depend on their perspectives to understand what different individuals and roles within these organizations are looking for in open technologies, including what health measures are most meaningful and influential for decision-making in local procurement and adoption environments.
- **Developers** - including a range of roles within open infrastructure providers, e.g., founders, directors, volunteers, committers, community managers, and product managers. Conducting this research and designing effective assessment methodologies that surface important information about the health of open infrastructures requires a deep understanding of the context and perspectives specific to each infrastructure provider. Assessing any group ethically and well, and portraying the results of that assessment in ways that benefit rather than harm that group, requires their ongoing engagement and input in the design and implementation of measures and methods.

Project recruitment and outreach will include:

1. Initial announcements and invitations, issued across our platforms and networks, including targeted information campaigns geared towards professional communities, working groups, and consortia in each sector (government, nonprofit, corporate).
2. Engagement with researchers working with CHAOSS measures and methods in other markets to learn from their work and to share our approaches and findings.
3. Engagement with the teams/working groups that have produced POSI and FOREST (note, the latter was co-authored by IOI’s Research Lead).
4. Ongoing, monthly information updates and input requests for all project partners, including interviewees and infrastructures.
5. Broad, open release of all findings.
6. Two open webinars, one to share initial information and invite participation, and one to share our findings and resulting recommendations.

Success and Impact

IOI was founded to build an evidence-base and actionable strategies to catalyze infrastructure investment and adoption in open research infrastructure. We engage deeply with institutional decision makers and funders, and we work collectively with open infrastructure providers to improve the embeddedness of, health of, and financing for these tools and services.

Through our work, we have heard institutional stakeholders and funders call for standardized measures to help them more effectively assess and identify infrastructure solutions to utilize and fund. Recent self-assessment efforts from infrastructure providers using evaluation frameworks (POSI, FOREST) demonstrate providers' desire to signal their adherence to good governance, management, and business practices.

We see tremendous promise in applying additional measures of health to the open infrastructures we monitor and champion – but also risk in setting up false comparisons if measures miss important context. In our preliminary research into CHAOSS' "bus factor", we saw interesting signals but also complexity in understanding whether fewer contributors to one infrastructure (who may be full-time, and serve as a dedicated implementation team) were in fact "better" or "more reliable" than projects that had more contributors but relied more on volunteer support. To be responsible steward-advocates, we believe that these measures should not exist in isolation; they should be identified, tested, and evaluated for potential risk with key stakeholders, including the infrastructures and those making funding and adoption decisions.

Our vision is to model a participatory approach to identifying, testing, and evaluating measures of community health that advances how we surface and evaluate infrastructure needs and value for funders, developers, and adopters. Pending the success of this approach, we hope to integrate these new measures into Infra Finder. The impact we intend is increased investment in and adoption of open infrastructure by each of the user groups with whom we are engaging.

Project Team

- **Katherine Skinner, PhD (Research Lead, IOI)** will supervise and assist with research protocol development, surveys, interviews, analysis, and synthesis work. Dr. Skinner, an open knowledge researcher-activist with deep commitments to community building was previously the founding director of the [Educopia Institute](#), where she co-founded and supported communities including [Library Publishing Coalition](#), [Software Preservation Network](#), and [Maintainers](#). She has PI-ed 26

grants with federal agencies and philanthropies. She has co-authored two frameworks: [Community Cultivation](#) (2018) and [FOREST](#) (2021) to guide communities towards fiscal and organizational health. At IOI, she leads our research projects and partnership work (e.g., NSF-funded “Investigating Reasonable Costs”).

- **Chrys Wu (Product Lead, IOI)** has been deeply engaged in the creation of Infra Finder and will work with Skinner on this project’s strategic direction and future integration scenarios; she will also help the team design and evaluate the open research infrastructure health measures. Wu has been a product manager, strategist, journalist, and consigliere, working with [GitHub](#), [O’Reilly Media](#), [The New York Times](#), [The Washington Post](#), the [Los Angeles Times](#), [DataKind](#), [The Knight Foundation](#), and [The Gates Foundation](#). She co-founded [Hacks/Hackers](#) (supporting local/global journalism innovation); and [Write/Speak/Code](#) (supporting marginalized genders in technology).
- **Lauren Collister, PhD (Engagement Coordinator, IOI)** will develop protocols; and conduct surveys and interviews; and code and analyze findings. She will lead the project’s engagement and communication strategy. Previously, as Director of Scholarly Communication at University of Pittsburgh, she led a diamond open-access publisher, advised on copyright, organized around labor issues, and managed communications. Collister holds a PhD in Linguistics. At IOI, she develops and leads our engagement strategy and conducts research (including playing a pivotal role in the development of Infra Finder).

Additional Questions

In which cost tier (incl. overhead costs) do you expect this work to sit? *

- Between 50K and 75K \$
- **Between 75K and 100K \$**
- (Specific budgets, connected with your provided tier, will be discussed after selection and are tied to the overall available budget and the selected portfolio)

How many months do you expect this work to take?

- 6-9 months
- **9-12 months**
- for part-time projects only: up to 14 months